

Supportive work environment for people with Down syndrome in Malaysia: a cross-sectional study

Md Mizanur Rahman¹, Chuong Hock Ting², Razitasham Safii¹, Rosalia Saimon¹, Yoke Yong Chen², Sharifa Ezat Wan Puteh³, Abg Safuan Adenan¹

¹Department of Community Medicine and Public Health, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Sarawak, Malaysia

²Department of Psychological Medicine, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak, Sarawak, Malaysia

³Department of Community Health, Faculty of Medicine, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia, Selangor, Malaysia

Article Info

Article history:

Received May 9, 2024

Revised Oct 30, 2024

Accepted Dec 13, 2024

Keywords:

Attitude

Down syndrome

Knowledge

Organizational culture

People with disabilities

ABSTRACT

Understanding organizational culture, knowledge of employment rights, and positive attitudes towards people with disabilities is crucial for creating inclusive workplaces. This Malaysian study compared the perspectives of employers, employees, and community members with disabilities using a cross-sectional design and convenience sampling of 595 respondents. Data on demographics, organizational culture, legislative knowledge, and attitudes were collected via a validated survey and analyzed using descriptive statistics, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA), and multiple linear regression in JAMOVI and SPSS, with a p -value $< .05$ indicating significance. The study found a moderately supportive organizational culture for employing people with disabilities, with the highest scores in supportive work environments and inclusive culture. Employers and employees perceived greater top management commitment and inclusivity than community members with Down syndrome. Legislative knowledge and positive attitudes significantly shaped perceptions of a supportive and inclusive workplace. Muslim participants reported greater support and disability-accommodating human resource (HR) practices than those of other religions. The findings underscore the need for targeted training and awareness programs on disability rights to enhance inclusivity among all stakeholders in Malaysia.

This is an open access article under the [CC BY-SA](#) license.

Corresponding Author:

Md Mizanur Rahman

Department of Community Medicine and Public Health, Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences

Universiti Malaysia Sarawak

St. Datuk Mohammad Musa, Samarahan, Sarawak, Malaysia

Email: rmmizanur@unimas.my, aniqm@hotmail.com

1. INTRODUCTION

The context of the inclusion of people with disability is moving very fast globally. World Health Organization (WHO) has underlined its acute importance for the development of society [1]. Thus, people with disabilities (PWDs) are represented superficially in key policy-making processes, as shown by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), which make the whole world committed to inclusion [2]. More and more financial resources are spent to safeguard the well-being of PWDs, as shown, for example, by initiatives such as those from the International Labor Organization to foster independence through work [3]. For persons with disabilities especially, a job is not just a source of income but one way of increasing one's self-sufficiency and independence in light of sustainable development [4]. People with disabilities face many barriers to getting jobs, especially those with Down syndrome, because of rampant misconceptions about their capabilities [5].

In Malaysia, people with Down syndrome face unique challenges in finding employment. It has been postulated that, despite the great potential of persons with Down syndrome to work, current employment rates for this group of people remain rather low [6]. This disparity is often blamed on employers' attitude, a lack of awareness about what individuals with Down syndrome can do, and a general shortage of suitable educational and training programs [4], [7]. This further explains that the cultural and social aspects add to the difficulties of getting the job [8], [9]. Thus, this study would help to understand the specific issues of employability for persons with disabilities in Malaysia. This is a huge barrier in employing people with Down syndrome, where little effective intervention has as yet taken place in either inclusive practices or legislation within Malaysian workplaces [4], [10].

Several strategies have been suggested to address these issues, including extensive training programmes and awareness initiatives targeting employers to create a more welcoming work environment for people with Down syndrome. These efforts should emphasise educating employers about the abilities of persons with Down syndrome and the advantages of inclusive recruitment practices [11]. Moreover, the public and private sectors must work together to establish a supportive framework for employing disabled individuals [12]. This research aims to investigate the current status of supportive work environments for people with Down syndrome in Malaysia, evaluating the efficacy of existing policies and practices whilst identifying areas that require improvement. By exploring these matters, the study seeks to contribute to the wider discussion on disability inclusion and encourage sustainable job opportunities for individuals with Down syndrome in Malaysia.

2. METHOD

2.1. Population and setting

A cross-sectional study was conducted among working adults aged 18 years and over in Malaysia between March 2022 and April 2023. Malaysia is a developing country in Southeast Asia, with an estimated population of 33.4 million in 2023 [13]. In February 2023, the number of employed persons was 18.19 million (67.4% of the total population). Among them, employees consistently comprise the largest group of employed people, 75.7% [14].

2.2. Sample size and sampling procedure

Due to the lack of a readily available sampling frame, this study employed a convenience sampling procedure. Although this method introduces potential biases, a deliberate effort was made to ensure greater precision in the results by aiming to collect a minimum sample size of 200 individuals for each of the three respondent categories: employers, employees (co-workers), and community members of PWDs. Participants were recruited from all Malaysian states through various channels, including email and digital media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. To be eligible for participation, individuals had to be at least 18 years old, hold Malaysian citizenship, and possess basic knowledge about disabilities, including Down syndrome, ensuring they were legally adults, connected to the Malaysian context, and familiar with the study's subject matter. Exclusion criteria included unwillingness to participate, inability to understand Bahasa Melayu, English, or Mandarin, lack of mental soundness, and having Down syndrome.

2.3. Data collection instrument and data collection procedure

We used a questionnaire to obtain demographic information about participants, including respondents' groups, ages, genders, ethnicities, educational levels, marital statuses, and religions. The questionnaire on organizational culture was adapted from a previous study [15]. The questionnaire on legislative knowledge of employment rights and attitudes towards disability in the workplace was adapted from a previous study [16]. However, we slightly modified the language to fit the local context while maintaining the original content. Before data collection, the questionnaire was sent to seven content experts (Researchers involved in the study related to people with down syndrome (PDS)) and language experts (Malay and Chinese teachers who understand their respective language and English language) for validation. We translated the questionnaire forward and backward into Malay and Chinese to ensure the English terms were correctly understood and translated. The questionnaire was then piloted on 50 working adults with various educational levels, and no modifications were required. The self-administered questionnaire was distributed to different companies based on the Malaysia business directory (www.businesslist.my), which covers a wide range of business categories. We also sought and received help from the village headman to select community members.

2.4. Measures

The organizational factors were adapted from the questionnaire developed by Maini and Heera [15]. It consists of 27 items with four factors: top management commitment (8 items), inclusive culture (9 items), supportive workplace (5 items), and disability-human resource management (HRM) fit (5 items). Responses

were obtained on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 (relevant to a small extent) to 5 (relevant to a very great extent). A higher score indicates a good organizational culture. The operational definitions of organizational culture and its subdomains are as follows:

- i) Organizational culture can be defined as the collective set of values, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors that characterize how an organization operates and interacts with its members, stakeholders, and external environment, particularly in the inclusion of disability [17]. It encompasses the organization's overarching atmosphere, norms and practices, as reflected in the commitment of top management, inclusive culture, supportive work environment, and HRM fit for disability. Operational definitions for the four domains of organizational culture related to top management commitment, inclusive culture, supportive workplace, and disability HRM fit, based on the provided statements, can be outlined as follows.
 - Top management commitment: This domain refers to how senior leadership demonstrates awareness and commitment to policies and practices concerning workers with disabilities, particularly those with Down syndrome. It involves establishing formal procedures, policies, and active support for the employment, promotion, and career advancement of individuals with disabilities. It also encompasses written policies on non-discrimination, accommodation requests, and equal opportunities for workers with disabilities.
 - Inclusive culture: This domain pertains to the organizational culture's attitude and actions toward workers with disabilities, including persons with Down syndrome. It reflects the organizations' concern for the well-being and opinions of these individuals and their perceived value as workforce members. It also includes the organizations' belief in the benefits of employing individuals with disabilities for its corporate image and its commitment to diversity and inclusivity in the workplace.
 - Supportive workplace: This domain assesses the extent to which the organization provides practical assistance, understanding, and forgiveness to workers with disabilities, including those with Down syndrome. It involves the willingness to help, provide support, and accommodate people with disabilities in their work environment. It also includes the organization's openness to employing individuals with disabilities and its general supportiveness toward all employees.
 - Disability HRM-fit: This domain evaluates the organization's effectiveness in managing human resources related to disability inclusion, particularly for people with Down syndrome. It encompasses the organization's ability to recruit individuals with disabilities, match jobs with their abilities, and provide timely and appropriate accommodations. It also involves handling terminations, if necessary, fairly and respectfully. It also includes training to increase awareness and sensitivity to disability among all employees.
- ii) Knowledge of employment rights for persons with disabilities. The instrument was derived from the questionnaire designed by Meager *et al.* [16] of the Institute for Employment Studies of the United Kingdom to assess the awareness, knowledge, and exercise of employment rights. The 14-item questionnaire comprises two parts: awareness of employment rights (10 items) and attitude towards legislation (4 items). The metrics for each item are based on a 5-point Likert scale from strongly disagree to strongly agree. A higher score indicates a higher knowledge of employment rights for people with disabilities.
- iii) Legislative knowledge of employment rights refers to individual awareness and understanding of the legal rights and protections afforded to people with disabilities in the workplace. It includes knowing specific laws, regulations, and policies that protect the rights of individuals with disabilities, including their right to work, seek help or advice, obtain information, address work-related problems, and take legal action if necessary. It also involves being informed about the relevant agencies or authorities responsible for enforcing these laws and knowing how to report violations or seek help.
- iv) Attitude towards disability in the workplace refers to individual beliefs, opinions, and perceptions regarding employment rights and treatment of persons with disabilities in the workplace. It involves attitudes towards inclusivity, non-discrimination, fairness, and equal opportunities for individuals with disabilities. Positive attitudes include recognizing the importance of learning about the rights of persons with disabilities, advocating for their employment, and ensuring fair treatment and opportunities for training and promotion. Negative attitudes may include the belief that employers should be required to employ a certain percentage of persons with disabilities or skepticism about the need to learn more about disability rights at work.

2.5. Statistical analysis

Since the data was collected through an online survey, it was entered directly into Microsoft Excel for the initial organization. Subsequently, data cleaning was performed to identify and address any inconsistencies within the dataset. The missing values were then examined, and missing data imputation techniques were employed using the built-in missing value modules in SPSS version 29.0. Descriptive statistics were generated to summarize the data. This included calculating means and standard deviations

(SD) for quantitative variables, while categorical variables were presented using frequencies and percentages. A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to explore potential differences in mean scores for organizational culture, knowledge of disability legislation, and workplace attitude toward people with disabilities in the three respondent categories. Significant findings of ANOVA were further investigated using post hoc comparisons with Bonferroni correction to determine the groups that differed. Finally, multiple linear regression analyses were performed for each domain to examine the relationships between sociodemographic characteristics and the various domains of organizational culture. JAMOVI version 2.3.28, an open-source statistical software, did this part of the data analysis. A significance level of $p < .05$ was adopted throughout the analysis to identify statistically significant relationships.

2.6. Ethical considerations

This study adhered to ethical principles throughout. The digital informed consent ensured that participants were fully informed before participation. Data confidentiality was maintained, and anonymity was guaranteed to protect participant privacy. Participants were also informed of their right to withdraw at any time, and all data was protected with passwords to prevent unauthorized access.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Characteristics of the respondents

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of 595 respondents in a study on employment for individuals with Down syndrome in Malaysia. The sample had a mean age of 36.3 years ($SD = 11.9$) and was predominantly female (59.8%). Respondents were categorized as employers (29.4%), employees (53.1%), and members of the community of persons with disabilities (PWDs) (17.5%). The majority held permanent employment (82.9%), were of Chinese ethnicity (72.3%), and had higher secondary education (58.2%). Most respondents were single (52.4%) and Christian (57.0%). The nature of jobs was diverse, with the service sector being the most common (44.0%), followed by official (28.7%) and manual jobs (27.2%).

3.2. Descriptive statistics

The study involving 595 participants revealed a moderate organizational culture that supports the employment of people with disabilities (PWD), with an overall mean score of 53.93% ($SD = 18.39\%$). Among the various dimensions assessed, the 'Supportive Workplace' aspect was perceived most positively ($M = 62.26\%$, $SD = 20.04\%$), indicating that participants generally feel their organizations provide a supportive environment for PWD. This finding is consistent with previous research highlighting the importance of a supportive workplace in enhancing job satisfaction and retention among employees with disabilities [18], [19]. The 'Inclusive Culture' dimension also scored relatively high ($M = 55.26\%$, $SD = 19.57\%$), suggesting that participants recognize efforts towards inclusivity within their organizations. However, the 'Top Management Commitment' score ($M = 49.62\%$, $SD = 20.76\%$) was slightly lower, indicating potential gaps in the visible and active support from top management. This aligns with existing literature that emphasizes the critical role of top management in driving and sustaining inclusive practices [20]. The 'Disability HRM-Fit' dimension had the lowest mean score ($M = 41.78\%$, $SD = 18.45\%$), highlighting an area for significant improvement. Effective HRM practices tailored to the needs of PWD are essential for their successful integration and career development within organizations [21]. The low score in this dimension suggests that current HRM practices may not be adequately addressing the unique needs of employees with disabilities. Participants demonstrated good legislative knowledge ($M = 74.86\%$, $SD = 14.57\%$), which is crucial for ensuring compliance with legal requirements and fostering a culture of inclusivity. Additionally, the positive attitudes towards the employment of PWD ($M = 57.88\%$, $SD = 17.69\%$) reflect a generally favorable disposition among participants, which can reduce stigma and promote a more inclusive workplace [22]. The study's subscales and overall measures demonstrated good to excellent internal reliability, with Cronbach's alphas ranging from .768 to .959. This high reliability indicates that the measures used in the study are consistent and dependable [23]. Furthermore, the moderate to strong correlations between individual items and their respective scales (corrected item-total correlations ranging from .353 to .812) suggest strong item discrimination, reinforcing the validity of the constructs being measured, as shown in Table 2 [24].

3.3. One-way ANOVA of the domains of organizational culture, knowledge, and attitude

Table 3 depicts the ANOVA findings, revealing significant differences between employers, employees, and community stakeholders in various organizational cultures relevant to the employment of people with disabilities (PWD). Notably, the community group demonstrated the highest perception of support in a 'Supportive Workplace' ($F(2, 594) = 21.623$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .068$), followed by employers and employees. This aligns with previous research indicating that community stakeholders often advocate more strongly for inclusive practices and support systems for PWD [18], [19]. Furthermore, the community group reported the highest level of knowledge in legislation ($F(2, 594) = 13.909$, $p < .001$, $\eta^2 = .045$), which is critical

given the importance of legal frameworks in promoting workplace inclusivity [20]. This finding suggests that community stakeholders might be more engaged with or informed about legal requirements and protections for PWD, potentially influencing their advocacy efforts. The community group also exhibited the most positive attitudes towards PWD ($F(2, 594)=6.072, p=.002, \eta^2=.020$). Positive attitudes are essential for fostering an inclusive workplace culture, as they can mitigate perceptual and attitudinal barriers that often hinder the employment and integration of PWD [21], [22]. Although significant ANOVA results emerged for 'Disability HRM-Fit' ($F(2, 594)=4.309, p=.014, \eta^2=.014$) and 'Inclusive Culture' ($F(2, 594)=2.864, p=.059, \eta^2=.010$), post-hoc comparisons with Bonferroni correction did not pinpoint the specific groups responsible for these differences. This suggests that while there are variations in perceptions, the differences are not strong enough to be attributed to specific groups conclusively. This finding underscores the complexity of achieving a cohesive, inclusive culture within organizations [25]. Interestingly, no significant differences were found in the perception of 'Top Management Commitment' ($F(2, 594)=0.703, p>.05, \eta^2=.002$). This lack of significant difference might indicate a general consensus or uniformity in how top management commitment is perceived across different groups, highlighting a potential area for organizational improvement to ensure top management's active and visible commitment to inclusivity [18], [19].

Table 1. Characteristics of the respondents (N = 595)

Characteristics	N	%/Mean (sd)
Age in years		36.3(11.9) years
Gender		
Female	356	59.8
Male	239	40.2
Respondents		
Employer	175	29.4
Employee	316	53.1
Community of PWDs	104	17.5
Employment status		
Permanent	493	82.9
Temporary/part-time	86	14.5
Volunteer	16	2.7
Ethnicity		
Malay	74	12.4
Chinese	430	72.3
Others (Iban, Bidayuh, and orang ulu)	91	15.3
Level of education		
Primary education	33	5.5
Secondary education	142	23.9
Higher secondary	346	58.2
Graduate and above	74	12.4
Marital status		
Single	312	52.4
Married	263	44.2
Others (Separated, widowed or divorced)	20	3.4
Religion		
Islam	87	14.6
Christian	339	57.0
Buddhism	131	22.0
Others (free thinkers, and Hinduism)	38	6.4
Nature of the job		
Official	171	28.7
Manual job	162	27.2
Service sector	262	44.0

τ Service sector includes health, sale and marketing, art, and entertainment

Table 2. Descriptive statistics of the organizational culture to employ a person with disabilities (N = 595)

Domains	# items	Mean %	Sd	95% CI	Cronbach alpha	Corrected item-total correlation
Organizational culture						
Top management commitment	8	49.62	20.8	48.0, 51.3	.911	.647-.758
Inclusive culture	9	55.26	19.6	53.7, 56.8	.890	.372-.809
Supportive workplace	5	62.26	20.0	60.7, 63.9	.822	.442-.735
Disability HRM-fit	5	41.78	18.5	40.3, 43.3	.919	.766-.811
Overall	27	53.93	18.4	52.5, 55.4	.959	.353-.78
Legislative knowledge and attitudes						
Legislative knowledge	10	57.88	17.7	56.5, 59.3	.947	.698-.812
Attitude	4	74.86	14.6	73.7, 76.0	.768	.485-.693

Table 3. One-way analysis of variance of domains of organizational culture, knowledge and attitude towards the employment of a person with disabilities by category of respondents (N = 595)

Variables	Employers (n = 175)	Employee (n = 316)	Employee (n = 104)	p-value	η^2
Top management commitment	48.2 (22.6)	49.9 (21.4)	51.1 (14.8)	p>.05	.002
Inclusive culture	57.4 (20.0)*	55.2 (20.5)	51.7 (15.2)*	p=.058	.010
Supportive Workplace	62.2 (19.5)*	58.7 (19.2)*	73.1 (19.8)*	p<.001	.068
Disability HRM fit	39.8 (18.8)*	41.4 (18.6)*	46.3 (16.9)*	p=.014	.014
Knowledge of the legislation	71.7 (15.1)*	74.6 (14.0)*	81.0 (13.5)*	p<.001	.045
Attitude	54.6 (19.6)*	58.3 (16.2)	62.1 (17.8)*	p=.002	.020

The figure in parentheses indicates sample size; an asterisk sign indicates post hoc differences.

3.4. Factors associated with the domains of organizational culture: multiple linear regression analysis

The multiple linear regression analysis conducted in Table 4 aimed to identify predictors associated with different domains of organizational culture, specifically focusing on the commitment of top management, inclusive culture, supportive workplace, and HRM fit for disability. Several predictor variables were included in the analysis, such as age, category of respondents, gender, ethnic group, level of education, marital status, religion, legislative knowledge, and attitude.

The multiple linear regression model explained 26% of the variance in top management commitment towards disability inclusion ($R^2 = 0.26$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.239$, $F(16, 578)=12.7$, $p<.001$). This finding underscores the importance of various factors in shaping management's commitment to fostering an inclusive workplace for people with disabilities (PWD). Significant predictors of top management commitment included the category of employers ($\beta=.37$, $p<.001$) and employees ($\beta=.30$, $p<.001$), who demonstrated higher perceived commitment than members of the disability community. This suggests that those within the organizational structure, such as employers and employees, may have a more favorable view of top management's commitment compared to those from the disability community. This aligns with the literature indicating that internal stakeholders often perceive organizational efforts more positively due to direct involvement and communication [15]. Ethnic Chinese participants were negatively associated with perceived top management commitment ($\beta=-.33$, $p<.01$). This may reflect cultural or systemic barriers that need to be addressed to ensure equitable inclusion across diverse ethnic groups [26]. Additionally, higher secondary education ($\beta=-.36$, $p<.01$) and graduate-level education ($\beta=-.47$, $p<.01$) were also negatively associated with commitment. This could indicate that individuals with higher education levels may have higher expectations or more critical views of management's efforts in disability inclusion [27]. Interestingly, attitudes towards PWD were positively associated with higher secondary education ($\beta=.41$, $p<.001$), suggesting that education plays a role in shaping positive perceptions and attitudes towards disability inclusion. This finding is consistent with research highlighting the role of education in fostering inclusive attitudes and reducing stigma [18].

In terms of creating an inclusive culture, the regression model explained 22% of the variance ($R^2=0.221$, adjusted $R^2=0.200$, $F(16, 578)=10.3$, $p<.001$). Employers ($\beta=.75$, $p<.001$) and employees ($\beta=.51$, $p<.001$) perceived a significantly greater level of inclusivity than community members with disabilities. Legislative knowledge ($\beta=.16$, $p<.001$) and attitudes towards PWD ($\beta=.32$, $p<.001$) were positively associated with perceived inclusive culture, reinforcing the importance of awareness and positive attitudes in promoting inclusivity [28].

For perceptions of a supportive workplace, the model explained 20.3% of the variance ($R^2=0.203$, adjusted $R^2=0.181$, $F(16, 578)=9.22$, $p<.001$). Community members with disabilities perceived the workplace to be significantly less supportive ($\beta=-.42$, $p<.001$), highlighting the need for more robust support structures. Higher levels of education were also negatively associated with perceptions of support ($\beta=-.32$, $p<.05$), which may reflect higher expectations or critical evaluations by more educated individuals [29]. Identifying as Muslim was positively associated with a supportive workplace ($\beta=.70$, $p<.001$), suggesting that cultural or religious values may influence perceptions of support [30].

Finally, the model explained 22.1% of the variance in HRM disability fit ($R^2=0.221$, adjusted $R^2=0.199$, $F(16, 578)=10.2$, $p<.001$). Positive attitudes towards PWD ($\beta=.36$, $p<.001$) and legislative knowledge were significant predictors of a stronger perceived HRM fit for disability. The perceived HRM fit was higher among those identifying as Muslim ($\beta=.65$, $p<.001$), indicating that cultural or religious contexts may play a role in shaping HRM practices [18].

Our analysis revealed that Malaysia has a moderately supportive organizational culture for employing people with Down syndrome (PDS). Supportive workplaces and inclusive cultures were most strongly perceived, where top management commitment and disability HRM fit were areas for improvement. Stakeholder groups such as employers, employees, and community members with disabilities demonstrated significantly different perspectives, highlighting the complexity of shaping disability-inclusive workplaces. However, our study encountered some limitations. Using an online survey may limit the generalizability of the results, as individuals without Internet access or familiarity with online platforms would be excluded. In addition, the reliance on self-reported data introduces a potential response bias, where participants may

provide socially desirable responses rather than entirely accurate perceptions. Furthermore, the cross-sectional design prevents the establishment of causal relationships between variables. Finally, the sample size, although substantial, was not obtained through random selection, which may further impact the representativeness of the findings. Additionally, incorporating qualitative data collection would provide richer information on the experiences of people with disabilities in different workplace settings.

Table 4. Factors associated with the domains of organizational culture: multiple linear regression analysis

Predictor	Top management commitment			Inclusive culture			Supportive workplace			Disability HRM-Fit		
	β	LL	UL	β	LL	UL	β	LL	UL	β	LL	UL
Intercept a	13.5			7.11			33.7			14.1		
Age in years	-0.01	-0.10	0.08	0.06	-0.04	0.15	0.05	-0.05	0.15	-0.02	-0.11	0.08
Respondents												
Community	-			-			-			-		
Employer	0.37***	0.12	0.61	0.75***	0.50	1.00	-0.17	-0.43	0.09	0.105	-0.20	0.31
Employee	0.30**	0.07	0.54	0.51***	0.27	0.76	-0.42***	-0.66	-0.17	-0.04	-0.29	0.20
Gender												
Female	-			-			-			-		
Male	0.04	-0.10	0.19	0.06	-0.09	0.21	0.15	0.00	0.31	0.04	-0.11	0.18
Ethnic group												
Malay	-0.22	-0.74	0.30	-0.16	-0.70	0.38	-0.39	-0.93	0.16	-0.32	-0.85	0.22
Chinese	-0.33**	-0.58	-0.08	-0.16	-0.42	0.09	-0.12	-0.38	0.13	-0.31	-0.56	-0.06
Others	-			-			-			-		
Level of education												
Primary	-			-			-			-		
Secondary education	-0.31	-0.65	0.04	-0.21	-0.56	0.15	-0.24	-0.60	0.12	-0.05	-0.41	0.30
Higher secondary	-0.36*	-0.71	-0.01	-0.33	-0.69	0.03	-0.38*	-0.75	-0.02	-0.22	-0.58	0.14
Graduate and above	-0.47*	-0.86	-0.09	-0.33	-0.72	0.07	-0.34	-0.74	0.06	-0.19	-0.59	0.21
Marital status												
Single	0.35	-0.09	0.78	0.37	-0.08	0.81	0.31	-0.14	0.76	0.50	0.06	0.95
Married	0.23	-0.18	0.64	0.12	-0.30	0.54	0.13	-0.30	0.55	0.20	-0.22	0.62
Others	-			-			-			-		
Religion												
Islam	0.48	-0.10	1.06	0.46	-0.14	1.05	0.70*	0.10	1.31	0.65*	0.05	1.25
Christian	0.07	-0.23	0.37	0.02	-0.28	0.33	0.17	-0.13	0.48	0.29	-0.02	0.59
Buddhism	0.03	-0.30	0.36	0.00	-0.33	0.33	0.14	-0.20	0.47	0.30	-0.04	0.63
Others	-			-			-			-		
Legislative knowledge	0.07	-0.01	0.14	0.16***	0.08	0.24	0.14***	0.06	0.22	0.02	-0.06	0.10
Attitude towards PDS	0.41***	0.34	0.49	0.32***	0.25	0.40	0.23***	0.15	0.31	0.36***	0.28	0.44
	R ² =0.260; Adj R ² =0.239 F(df ₁ , df ₂)=12.7(16, 578); p<.001			R ² =0.221; Adj R ² =0.200 F(df ₁ , df ₂)=10.3(16, 578); p<.001			R ² =0.203; Adj R ² =0.181 F(df ₁ , df ₂)=9.22(16, 578); p<.001			R ² =0.221; Adj R ² =0.199 F(df ₁ , df ₂)=10.2(16, 578); p<.001		

LL= Lower limit of 95% confidence interval; UL= Upper limit of 95% confidence interval; *p<.05; **p<.01; ***p<.001

4. CONCLUSION

In general, respondents were moderately positive, with the highest endorsement of a supportive workplace. Stakeholders (employers, employees, community members) differed in their views. The community group perceived the most supportive workplace and knew the most about relevant legislation. They also expressed the most positive attitudes towards PDS in the workplace. However, employers and employees perceived greater commitment and inclusion of top management. To cultivate a more inclusive environment, targeted education initiatives, strengthened disability-focused HR practices, and visible management support for disability inclusion were recommended.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

We sincerely thank the participants who volunteered for this study, especially considering the difficulties presented by the COVID-19 pandemic. The authors appreciate the approval of the Faculty Ethics Committee of this research (Ref # FME/21/12). The funding for this project was kindly provided by the Ministry of Higher Education of Malaysia (Ref #: FRGS/1/2020/SS0/UNIMAS/01/2), and we are grateful for the support of Universiti Malaysia Sarawak. The authors thank Prof. Andrew Kiyu, Department of Community Medicine and Public Health, for his generous support in manuscript editing and scholarly comments for the improvement of the article.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The Ministry of Higher Education of Malaysia funded this research (Ref: Fundamental Research Grant Scheme, FRGS/1/2020/SS0/UNIMAS/01/2).

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

Name of Author	C	M	So	Va	Fo	I	R	D	O	E	Vi	Su	P	Fu
Md Mizanur Rahman	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Chuong Hock Ting	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Razitasham Safii	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Rosalia Saimon	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Yoke Yong Chen	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Sharifa Ezat Wan Puteh	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
Abg Safuan Adenan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

INFORMED CONSENT

The study began only after all its participants provided their informed consent by demonstrating their complete understanding of the research goals and method, potential risks, and benefits involved. Research participants received detailed explanations that were easy to understand so they could understand the study well enough to decide whether they wanted to take part. Participants received specific information about their right to leave the study anytime without needing to provide explanations or fear negative effects. Research principles along with individual autonomy and rights received complete protection through the voluntary nature of study participation.

ETHICAL APPROVAL

Before initiating the data-gathering process, ethical clearance was obtained from the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences at Universiti Malaysia Sarawak (Ref # FME/21/12). This crucial step ensures that the research complies with established ethical guidelines and safeguards participants' rights, safety, and welfare. The ethics committee comprehensively evaluates the research proposal to assess potential risks, verify informed consent procedures, safeguard confidentiality, and maintain the study's integrity.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author, [MMR]. The data, which contain information that could compromise the privacy of research participants, are not publicly available due to certain restrictions.

REFERENCES

- [1] World Health Organization, "Disability and Health." <https://www.who.int/health-topics/disability> (accessed Mar. 13, 2024).
- [2] United Nations, "Transforming our world: The 2030 agenda for sustainable development," *Department of Economic and Social Affairs Sustainable Development*, 2015.
- [3] International Labour Organization, "World Employment and Social Outlook: Trends 2021," *International Labour Organization*, 2021.

- [4] S. Lindsay, E. Cagliostro, M. Albarico, N. Mortaji, and L. Karon, "A systematic review of the benefits of hiring people with disabilities," *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, vol. 28, no. 4, pp. 634–655, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s10926-018-9756-z.
- [5] B. G. Skotko, S. P. Levine, and R. Goldstein, "Having a brother or sister with Down syndrome: Perspectives from siblings," *American Journal of Medical Genetics Part A*, vol. 155, no. 10, pp. 2348–2359, Oct. 2011, doi: 10.1002/ajmg.a.34228.
- [6] L. Kumin and L. Schoenbrodt, "Employment in adults with Down syndrome in the United States: Results from a national survey," *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 330–345, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1111/jar.12182.
- [7] L. Nota, S. Santilli, M. C. Ginevra, and S. Soresi, "Employer attitudes towards the work inclusion of people with disability," *Journal of Applied Research in Intellectual Disabilities*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 511–520, Nov. 2014, doi: 10.1111/jar.12081.
- [8] A. R. A. Manaf, S. Z. Othman, M. F. M. Isa, W. S. M. M. Noor, and N. Azizan, "Employment challenges among persons with disabilities in Malaysia," *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, vol. 9, no. 10, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.6007/IJARBS/v9-i10/6469.
- [9] V. Sundar *et al.*, "Striving to work and overcoming barriers: Employment strategies and successes of people with disabilities," *Journal of Vocational Rehabilitation*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 93–109, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.3233/JVR-170918.
- [10] S. J. Macdonald and L. Deacon, *Disability theory and social work practice*. The Routledge Handbook of Social Work Theory, 2019. doi: 10.4324/9781315211053-39.
- [11] M. Satzger and R. Vogel, "Do inclusive workplace policies foster employer attractiveness? Comparative evidence from an online employer review platform," *Public Personnel Management*, vol. 52, no. 4, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1177/00910260231187536.
- [12] Q. Aqsa and B. Y. Nugroho, "A literature review: Cross-sector collaboration arrangements to deliver public services and goods," *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, vol. 40, pp. 1–10, Feb. 2023, doi: 10.47577/tssj.v40i1.8342.
- [13] Department of Statistics Malaysia, "Current population estimates, Malaysia," 2023. <https://www.dosm.gov.my/portal-main/release-content/current-population-estimates-malaysia-2023> (accessed Mar. 06, 2024).
- [14] D. of S. Malaysia, "Key statistics of labour force in Malaysia," *Department of Statistics Malaysia*. https://v1.dosm.gov.my/v1/index.php?r=column/cthemByCat&cat=124&bul_id=Z05rK25YRVF5SVFTcUU5dElAZ2tQT09&menu_id=Tm8zcnRjdVRNWwlpWjRlbnmtlaDk1UT09 (accessed Mar. 20, 2002).
- [15] A. Maini and S. Heera, "Exploring disability inclusion in organizations through managerial lens," *Vision: The Journal of Business Perspective*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 144–151, Jun. 2019, doi: 10.1177/0972262919840193.
- [16] N. Meager, C. Tyers, S. Perryman, J. Rick, and R. Willison, "Awareness, knowledge and exercise of individual employment rights," *Labour Market Trends*, no. 15, 2002.
- [17] K. Wong., "Organizational culture: Definition, importance, and development." <https://www.achievers.com/blog/organizational-culture-definition/> (accessed Mar. 13, 2024).
- [18] L. Schur, D. Kruse, and P. Blanck, "Corporate culture and the employment of persons with disabilities," *Behavioral Sciences & the Law*, vol. 23, no. 1, pp. 3–20, Jan. 2005, doi: 10.1002/bsl.624.
- [19] L. Schur, D. Kruse, J. Blasi, and P. Blanck, "Is disability disabling in all workplaces? Workplace disparities and corporate culture," *Industrial Relations: A Journal of Economy and Society*, vol. 48, no. 3, Jul. 2009, doi: 10.1111/j.1468-232X.2009.00565.x.
- [20] L. H. Nishii, D. P. Lepak, and B. Schneider, "Employee attributions of the 'why' of HR practices: their effects on employee attitudes and behaviors, and customer satisfaction," *Personnel Psychology*, vol. 61, no. 3, Sep. 2008, doi: 10.1111/j.1744-6570.2008.00121.x.
- [21] A. M. Santuzzi and P. R. Waltz, "Disability in the workplace: A unique and variable identity," *Journal of Management*, vol. 42, no. 5, pp. 1111–1135, Jul. 2016, doi: 10.1177/0149206315626269.
- [22] N. Mik-Meyer, "Othering, ableism and disability: A discursive analysis of co-workers' construction of colleagues with visible impairments," *Human Relations*, vol. 69, no. 6, pp. 1341–1363, Jun. 2016, doi: 10.1177/0018726715618454.
- [23] K. S. Taber, "The use of cronbach's alpha when developing and reporting research instruments in science education," *Research in Science Education*, vol. 48, no. 6, pp. 1273–1296, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s11165-016-9602-2.
- [24] E. A. O. Zijlmans, J. Tijnstra, L. A. van der Ark, and K. Sijtsma, "Item-score reliability as a selection tool in test construction," *Frontiers in Psychology*, vol. 9, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2018.02298.
- [25] L. Schur, L. Nishii, M. Adya, D. Kruse, S. M. Bruyère, and P. Blanck, "Accommodating employees with and without disabilities," *Human Resource Management*, vol. 53, no. 4, pp. 593–621, Jul. 2014, doi: 10.1002/hrm.21607.
- [26] K. Vornholt, S. Uitdewilligen, and F. J. N. Nijhuis, "Factors affecting the acceptance of people with disabilities at work: A literature review," *Journal of Occupational Rehabilitation*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 463–475, Dec. 2013, doi: 10.1007/s10926-013-9426-0.
- [27] J. E. Robinson, "Access to employment for people with disabilities: findings of a consumer-led project," *Disability and Rehabilitation*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 246–253, Jan. 2000, doi: 10.1080/096382800296818.
- [28] J. Gasper, M. Palan, and B. Muz, *Survey of employer policies on the employment of people with disabilities: Final report*. Report prepared for the Chief Evaluation Office (CEO), Office of Disability Employment Policy (ODEP), 2020. vol. 3129, no. 301. 2020.
- [29] M. Kulkarni and M. L. Lengnick-Hall, "Socialization of people with disabilities in the workplace," *Human Resource Management*, vol. 50, no. 4, pp. 521–540, Jul. 2011, doi: 10.1002/hrm.20436.
- [30] H. Hammad *et al.*, "Influence of religiosity on youths' attitudes towards people with disabilities in the United Arab Emirates," *Journal of Religion and Health*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 2423–2442, Jun. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s10943-022-01646-x.

BIOGRAPHIES OF AUTHORS

Md Mizanur Rahman is an expert in public health and statistics, currently serving as a senior medical lecturer at Universiti Malaysia Sarawak for over 13 years. His research areas include Tobacco control, human disability, food safety, security, and nutrition. He can be contacted at email: rmmizanur@unimas.my or aniqm@hotmail.com.

Chuong Hock Ting is a medical lecturer and a psychiatrist at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, Universiti Malaysia Sarawak (UNIMAS). He worked with the Ministry of Health Malaysia and the Ministry of Health Holding Singapore for 7 years before joining UNIMAS 8 years ago. His research interests include public and mental health, prevention and intervention. He can be contacted at email: chting@unimas.my.

Razitasham Safii is a Public Health Medicine Specialist, currently working in Community Medicine and Public Health Department. Her specializations include family health, one health and field epidemiology. Her research interest includes adolescent health, mental health, special needs children, and communicable disease. She can be contacted at email: srazitasham@unimas.my.

Rosalia Saimon is a senior lecturer at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, UNIMAS. Her Ph.D. in Social and Preventive Medicine (Health Promotion) focuses on the bio-psycho-social needs of individuals and communities within dynamic environments with psychosocial stimuli that promote health and well-being. Her research interests include adolescent health, elderly health, mental health, and salutogenic built environment aspects. She can be contacted at email: srosalia@unimas.my.

Yoke Yong Chen is a senior lecturer at the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, UNIMAS, in the Malaysian Ministry of Health. Her Ph.D. in Psychology (Health) focuses on the relationship between traumatic experiences and post-traumatic stress disorder among patients with cardiovascular conditions. Her research addresses the holistic bio-psycho-social needs of individuals in both community and healthcare settings. Her work includes intervention studies and research on rehabilitation strategies. She can be contacted at email: yychen@unimas.my.

Sharifa Ezat binti Wan Puteh is a senior lecturer at the Department of Public Health Medicine, Faculty of Medicine, Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia. Her Ph.D. in Public Health-Health Economics focuses on HPV vaccine cost-effectiveness, shaping Malaysia's vaccination policy. She has held key academic and administrative roles, including Dean of the Centre for Citra Studies (PPCU), Deputy Dean, and Head of Case Mix & Coding. Actively involved in health policy, research, and consultancy, she collaborates with ministries, universities, and international bodies on health financing, smoking control, and public health reforms. She can be contacted at email: sh_ezat@hctm.um.edu.my.

Abg Safuan Adenan is a recent graduate in Public Health from the Faculty of Medicine and Health Sciences, UNIMAS. His postgraduate research work focuses on exploring the barriers and enhancers of employment for person with Down syndrome in Malaysia. His research interest includes social and preventive medicine, disability studies, and epidemiology. At the time of writing, he is currently a house officer serving under the Ministry of Health, Malaysia. He can be contacted at email: abgsafuan08@gmail.com.